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THE ORIGINS AND FORMATION OF LIBRARY CENSORSHIP IN UKRAINE

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The purpose of the work is to explore the history of the censorship establishment in the information library policy formation. Methodological basis of the investigation is a set of principles and scientific research methods developed by modern science. The principle of historicism is expressed in the account of all specific historical factors for determining the stages of formation of library censorship in Ukraine, the allocation of general and special in it. The method of objectivity was reflected in a weighted assessment and impartial analysis of the forms and directions of the embodiment of spiritual and secular censorship. Also, an analytical method was used to determine the principles of the centralized system of censorship bodies that regulated the activities of public libraries, in particular the creation of ministerial directories under which the cleaning of book funds took place. Scientific novelty is to reveal the influence of library censorship as a hindrance to the scientific and cultural development of society establishment of civil society democratic foundations.

Conclusions. The origins of the establishment of library censorship in Ukraine are revealed. The main stages, forms and directions of the spiritual and secular censorship embodiment are investigated. The influence of the Russian Empire censorship on the formation of a public libraries network and the Ukrainian-language literature extraction from the funds of public libraries has been analyzed. The principles of the centralized system of censorship bodies that regulated the activities of public libraries were followed, in particular, attention was paid to the creation of ministerial directories under which the cleaning of book funds took place. The essence of the censorship policy of the Russian government that was aimed at the destruction of public libraries of Ukraine as important centers of Ukrainian spirituality was revealed. The principles of work of the Soviet censorship institutions that regulated the directions of work of Ukrainian libraries, transforming them into institutions of political science were clarified.

Keywords: censorship; imperial censorship; Soviet censorship institutions; public libraries; library business; “cleaning” of the fund; ministerial directories.

Introduction

By forming a system of prohibitions on libraries, the state deliberately limits its information space. That is why the use of censorship by the state authorities leads to inhibition of the scientific and cultural development of society, the establishment of democratic foundations on which a civil society

is formed, the indicator of which is the level of ensuring freedom of speech and freedom of the press. In addition, freedom of speech is a guarantee of the lack of transparency in government decisions, public relations, the protection of information rights (which should be regarded as natural) of citizens and society as a whole, a condition for democratic development itself and the establishment of a democratic political culture. In this regard, the understanding of the library censorship policy essence becomes particularly relevant. In the conditions of the a free democratic society formation and socio-political transformations in Ukraine, an appeal to the history of the librarianship of Ukraine, in particular to such an aspect as the library censorship formation, becomes especially relevant. One of the main means of forming an information and library policy was and remains censorship. By forming a system of prohibitions on libraries, the state deliberately limits its information space. That is why the use by the state authorities of censorship leads to inhibition of the scientific and cultural development of society, the establishment of democratic foundations on which a civil society is formed, the indicator of which is the level of ensuring freedom of speech and freedom of the press. In addition, freedom of speech is a guarantee of the lack of transparency of government decisions, public relations, the protection of information rights (which should be considered as natural) of citizens and society as a whole, a condition for proper democratic development and the establishment of a democratic political culture.

The methodological basis of investigation is a set of scientific principles and methods developed by modern science. The principle of historicism is expressed in the account of all the specific historical factors for determining the stages of formation of library censorship in Ukraine, the allocation of general and special in it. The method of objectivity was reflected in a weighted assessment and impartial analysis of the forms and directions of the embodiment of spiritual and secular censorship. Also, an analytical method was used to determine the principles of the centralized system of censorship bodies that regulated the activities of public libraries, in particular the creation of ministerial directories under which book funds were cleaned.

One of the first studies, which highlights the origins of library censorship, is the exploration of I. Korneichyk "The History of Ukrainian Bibliography: The Pre-October Period: Essays", where the author identified the factors of the emergence of censorship that existed from the first libraries of the times of Kyiv Rus after the adoption of Christianity by the beginning of the twentieth century. (Korneychik, 1971). The prerequisites for the emergence and establishment of library censorship in Ukraine were to some extent covered in the writings of domestic scholars. So, V. Lutovinov in "The study of the process of forming a special bibliography in Ukraine for the assistance of education and self-education" (1998), reproducing the history of the emergence and formation of a scientific support and recommendation bibliography, analyzed the lists of "true" and "false" books.

T. Gorbachenko made a contribution to the development of the problem of identifying the sources of library censorship. In particular, one should mention her monograph "The Influence of Christianity on the Formation of the Written Culture of Kyiv Rus-Ukraine: Philosophical and Religious Aspect" (2001).

Thus, the analyzed literature made it possible to trace the origins of the formation and formation of library censorship, starting with the Kievan Rus, characterizes apocryphal works that were considered to be representatives of ecclesiastical authority denied, reveals the main sources of censorship and certain factors that negatively influenced the preservation of ancient Russian books.

In the collection “Rossirosiishchennia Ukrainy” (Russification of Ukraine) (1992) Ukrainian historians highlighted the main methods and means by which Russia has long tried to impose its ideology on the Ukrainian people. Therefore, M. Chivorskyi (1992) disclosed the aspects of introducing spiritual censorship over the cultural life of the Ukrainian people; L. Postanovy (1992) highlighted the main means by which the tsarist censorship of the Russian government destroyed Ukrainian culture; B. Romanenchuk (1992) analyzed the influence of tsarist censorship on the development of Ukrainian culture.

Kagamlyk S. R. (1994) disclosed the main methods of extracting literature from the library of the Kyiv-Pechersk Lavra, due to the disagreement between these works and the representatives of the Higher Synod – the main body of censorship, which implemented royal censorship in book and library business. On the basis of a large part of the archival sources (party, censorship, state, public) from the funds of state archival collections, the peculiarities of the implementation of censorship policy in Ukraine at various stages of its development were considered in the study of O. Fedotova (2009).

M. Tymoshyk’s works are characterized by the originality of thought and the latest approaches to the study of the main stages of the censorship development in publishing and librarianship (Tymoshyk, 2003; Tymoshyk, 2004). Censorship prohibitions on “written word” arose with the advent of writing. Its formation and design took place in the era of antiquity, when in Greece burned books about the Gods. During the Roman Empire, works that did not meet the interests of the ruling power were destroyed or prohibited for general use, and the authors were isolated from society (History of Printing: Anthology, Vol. 1, 2001, p. 24). Later, the clergy carried out a censorship of book distribution. The founder of spiritual censorship is the Pope Helisius, who concluded the first index of prohibited books “*Indexlibrorumprohibitorum*”, which led to the destruction of not only books but their authors.

The purpose of the article

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Presentation of the main material

In Kievan Rus, censorship was introduced after the adoption of Christianity, when there were manuscripts, mainly of religious content, originating from Byzantium and Bulgaria, and kept in funds of monastic libraries subordinated to the clergy, which followed their writing, translation and distribution. By

preventing the dissemination of anti-religious literature, Byzantine theologians created lists of literature that were forbidden for distribution. Having got to Kievan Rus, they got the names of the lists of “true” and “false” books. The lists of “false” books included works that were prohibited by the orthodox church for reading in libraries, and the list of “true” books belonged to literature that the clergy recommended for reading and distribution.

To the “falsely written”, “denied” or “secret” books belonged apocrypha. The interest in the apocrypha was due to the fact that they contained practical advice, helped to find answers to the questions related to the explanation of the natural phenomena of the surrounding world (Korneichyk, 1971, p. 11).

In the IX century lists of “true” and “false” books were made not only in “Izbornik” of Svyatoslav and “Tacticon” of Nikon Chernogroitsya, but also in the first Slavic type index, which entered into the “Pogodinsky Nomokanon” – a collection of statutory nature.

Since 1280, “Lists of apocryphal works” began to be introduced into “Korchma” and “Church statutes” – collections of rules laid out by the church and civil authorities, through which the church authorities influenced the socio-cultural development of society (Dictionary of Bookworld and scribes of Ancient Russia 11th and the first half of the 14th centuries, 1987).

The emergence of printing contributed to the consolidation of censorship by the two ruling forces – the church and the state, which sought to usurp over book printing.

In the Russian Empire in the 18th century spiritual censorship is backed up by the state, which became the most repressive in the nineteenth century, when the centralized system of censorship organs was formed and improved, which included the supervision of library business. The main purpose of the introduction of royal censorship was to strengthen the autocratic system of the Russian Empire, a part of which, as it is known, Ukraine was considered, or as it was then called – Malorossia (Little Russia). The introduction of strict censorship over the national-cultural life of the Ukrainian people was conditioned by Peter I attempts to limit the administrative autonomy of Ukraine with a view to full merger of Ukrainians with Russians and to obliterate Ukrainians from their national features (History of Press, Vol. 1). As you know, the main feature of the national dignity of the Ukrainian people was and is the language, which is why the censorship policy of the tsarist government was aimed at the complete destruction of the Ukrainian language. This was manifested in the removal from the funds of public libraries of Ukrainian-language literature, which concerned identity and culture of the Ukrainian people. Under the order of the Ministry of Religious Affairs and Public Education in 1824, for the first time, a massive “purge” of public libraries was carried out, which resulted in the destruction of hundreds of books.

The strengthening of censorship was confirmed by the creation in 1826 of the Supreme Censorship Committee, the main tasks of which included administrative supervision of the collection of funds of public libraries. The aim was to prevent the distribution of the literature among the population whose content contradicted the state policy and ideology; therefore, the works that

did not meet these requirements were withdrawn and destroyed (Kravchenko, 2000, p. 116).

The restoration of the Ukrainian movement in new forms has caused severe repression by the Russian government and marked the beginning of a new period of the struggle between official Russia and Ukrainian nationality. At that time, it was reflected in the destruction of the cultural heritage of the Ukrainian people. The government's actions against the revival of the national-cultural movement were reflected in the introduction of strict censorship, with the aim of limiting the spread of the Ukrainian language both in the press and in literary works. As M. Tymoshyk rightly pointed out, the main reason for the increase of censorship was "... the appearance of the first spiritualized Shevchenko muse, which reminded the "malorosy (Little Russians)" of their true homeland, their former glory and national dignity that was humiliated for centuries" (Tymoshyk, 2003, p. 232) about that, they had their own language. The main purpose of the imperial censorship was to restrict the spread of the Ukrainian language, because: "The language, its printed word, really united people, lifted them from the knees, prompted thinking and transformed them with this thinking from the "Malorosy (Little Russians)", "khokhols" to Ukrainians (Tymoshyk, 2003, p. 243).

Significantly increased censorship was promoted by Valuevskiy (1863) and Yamskiy (1876) decrees on the prohibition of the publication of Ukrainian publications and their use in public libraries. With this aim, the special state documents were prepared "Rules on Free People's Readings and the Procedure for Supervising them" (1888), "Alphabetical Listings of the Works of Printing Prohibited to Distribute in Public Libraries" (1894), which introduced a strict regulation of linguistic the composition of the funds of public libraries, the availability of the Ukrainian-language book, in particular, the works were to be edited by M. Lermontov, F. Dostoevskiy, V. Korolenko, A. Chekhov and T. Shevchenko.

In 1903 a new list of banned publications for public and folk libraries was prepared by the tsarist government; the works of such Ukrainian authors as Borys Grinchenko, M. Stasiuk, S. Cherkasenko, A. Shablenko, the reciter O. Kovalenko were included in the lists of prohibited literature. The main reason for their prohibition was content that did not meet the wishes of Russian censors, because their works revealed and glorified the identity of the Ukrainian people. This is evidenced by the report of the censor S. Kosovich, which was read at the meeting of the St. Petersburg Censorship Committee on June 15, 1892. Concerning B. Grinchenko's poem "Beatrice Chenchi" the censor reported: "The plot of the poems is the most uncomfortable, we can say, despicable. The fable is known. The author of the poem ends with an appeal to his native land – Ukraine" (Bilokin, 1990, p. 70).

The implementation of the censorship of the tsarist government in relation to Ukraine has become the cause of social tension, which has led to concern from prominent figures of the Ukrainian intelligentsia. Thus, in connection with the revision of the legislation on censorship and reform, B. D. Grinchenko wrote: "If in general the situation of printing in Russia is burdensome, the

situation of the Ukrainian print undergoes all the consequences of injustice, administrative arbitrariness and compulsory silence on the most pressing issues. life ... Ukrainian is already completely deprived of the opportunity to touch any issues, has long been limited in the right to exist and already since 1863 has been doomed to eradication” (Bilokin, 1990, p. 71).

The scale of the revolutionary movement in the country and the new outbreak of the national Ukrainian movement forced the government to make some concessions. At the end of 1904, in early 1905, censorial restrictions on Ukrainian writing were lifted: even Ukrainian publishers received permission to publish and distribute in the village and local libraries of the Ukrainian translation of the Four Gospels (1929), as well as fictional and historical literature. In addition, in December 1905, the rules for the supervision of public and public libraries were abolished.

But in 1910, according to the order of Stolypin, Ukrainian cultural societies, publishing houses were closed, and it was forbidden to read lectures in Ukrainian even in local Universities. The educational work was put to an end, and in 1912, tsarism revived the ministerial catalogues revoked by the revolution of 1905, which recommended literature for folk readers, “New rules on the organization of work of national book colleges” were adopted, which strengthened the censorship of Ukrainian-language works in public libraries (V. Sarbei, 1998).

The library censorship in Ukraine after the establishment of Soviet power took new forms. From the first days of the establishment of Soviet power, censorship became an integral part of Soviet librarianship policy, and public libraries, which in the Soviet era turned into masses, were viewed by the Bolshevik authorities as the main institutions of political education that promoted the spread of their ideology (Shapoval, 1993, p. 159).

One of the main means of censorship was the publication of certain circulars, the development of special instructions and provisions that defined the main directions of library activity, in particular the decrees of the CPC RFSR “On Press” (1917) and “On the Revolutionary Tribunal of Press” (1918), which contributed to the prohibition of so-called bourgeois publications, books, newspapers and magazines of non-Soviet orientation, initiating the Soviet censorship of book and library activities (Abramov, 1996, p. 67). The first means of Soviet library censorship can be considered the implementation of nationalization, requisition and confiscation of private bookshops and libraries of civic organizations, largely contributing to the decree of the RSFSR CPC “On the Protection of Libraries and Book Stores” and its annex “On the Procedure for the Recycling of Libraries, Book Stocks and Books in General” (1918), as well as the resolutions of the People’s Commissariat of the Ukrainian SSR, in particular, “On the requisition of libraries” (1919), which referred to the necessity of using violent acts – requisitioning and confiscation of books stock funds of libraries by government agencies and their transfer to the out-of-school department of the corresponding city or district department of public education (Kivshar, 1996).

A special role in the formation of Soviet librarianship censorship belonged to the Extraordinary Military Censorship, the introduction of “temporarily” in

the course of hostilities, the People's Commissariat of the Ukrainian SSR and its library section, under which the library sections of the provincial and district departments of extracurricular education carried out massive purges of library funds of libraries from religious, monarchical and mundane publications (Resolutions of the Ukrainian SSR, Protocols and excerpts from the minutes of meetings, consultations and sections, Central State Archives of Public Associations of Ukraine. F.1. F 20. It. 831. P. 189).

Since the centralization of the Soviet librarian censorship was central to the features of the Soviet library censorship, it was a question of the need to create centralized networks in the provinces, the fundamentals of which should have been made up of requisitioned and confiscated book collections. Some of the requisitioned and confiscated publications came to the newly formed public libraries, public organizations, and the rest were destroyed, rare and valuable publications were sent to Moscow or transferred to the "special guardians". One of the areas of Soviet censorship was the destruction of Ukrainian public organizations and their libraries, and therefore a fairly extensive network of libraries of the "Prosvita (Education)" and "Dytiacha hata (Children's house)" associations as "nationalist institutions" ceased to exist (Kivshar, 1996).

To create a flexible system for introducing censorship into the activity of libraries, the need was discussed for the construction of a single, public library network, the main task of which was the systematic propaganda of communist ideology. In the first years of its existence, the Soviet government began to form a state censorship apparatus, creating special structures that censored the supervision of the activities of public libraries, closing private libraries and libraries as the centers of Ukrainian spirituality, forming new types of Soviet libraries.

Conclusions

Thus, the beginning of librarian censorship, the essence of which was the organization of a system of actions and measures aimed at securing and serving the interests of power in Ukraine set up after the emergence of libraries and the adoption of Christianity, when the church authorities began to control the distribution of books and book use, introducing lists of "true" and "false" books that doped the dissemination of information in society, forbidding apocryphal works. The revision of the books and the permission to use them in worship led to the fact that apocryphal works began to be renounced, the specific principle of the selection of books to church monastic libraries and was doomed to the disappearance of literature that was not included in the recommended lists. Monastic libraries, which collected and stored all manuscript books, did not provide for the use of works that were not included in the list of "false" non-canonical books not recommended by the church for reading. As a result, this led to the fact that society did not have the opportunity to read the literature, which corresponded to its needs, which hindered the development of education and culture in Kiev Rus.

In connection with the changes in the political, socio-cultural life of the country, and with the advent of the printed book, secular censorship arose to prevent or disseminate information undesirable for the ruling power, which led to the emergence of special institutions – the Supreme Censorship Committee. The Main Directorate of Censorship, Censorship Committees (Kyiv, Odesa), the Committee of Internal Censorship in Kiev (1838). The specificity of the manifestation of the censorship legislation of the Russian Empire in relation to Ukrainian libraries was observed in the fact that the lists of literature intended to remove or prohibit the acquisition of public libraries were dominated by Ukrainian-language books. Consequently, secular censorship, in contrast to the spiritual, but the general political motives, was distinguished also by the national one. The library censorship policy of the Russian government aimed at banning public libraries as important centers of Ukrainian spirituality, which kept and concentrated literary monuments accumulated over many centuries and thus ensured the continuity of generations. The main purpose of the introduction of tsarist censorship was the inhibition of the powerful movement of national revival, which took place in the 1960s of 19th century and was marked by a rapid take-off of Ukrainian culture and literature, in particular, by the growth of national consciousness, and by the increased social activity.

The formation of Soviet censorship in the libraries of Ukraine took place under conditions of the destruction of the democratic foundations of the library business of the era of the Ukrainian People's Republic (1917–1920). The creation of state institutions of censorship contributed to the introduction of decrees and regulations of the RSFSR into the library construction of Ukraine, which was aimed at introducing strict censorship control over the activities of public libraries, which began with the nationalization, requisition and confiscation of their material and technical base, book funds and catalogues.

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ВИТОКИ ТА СТАНОВЛЕННЯ БІБЛІОТЕЧНОЇ ЦЕНЗУРИ В УКРАЇНІ

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Мета статті. Дослідити історію становлення цензури при формуванні інформаційно-бібліотечної політики. Методологічною основою розвідки є сукупність вироблених сучасною наукою принципів і методів наукового дослідження. Принцип історизму виражений в обліку всіх конкретно-історичних чинників для визначення етапів становлення бібліотечної цензури на Україні, виділення в ній загального й особливого. Метод об'єктивності знайшов відображення у зваженій оцінці та неупередженому аналізі форм і напрямків втілення духовної та світської цензури. Також використано аналітичний метод для визначення принципів роботи централізованої системи цензурних органів, які регламентували напрями діяльності публічних бібліотек, зокрема створенні міністерських каталогів згідно з якими відбувалась чистка книжкових фондів. Наукова новизна полягає у виявленні впливу бібліотечної цензури як гальмівного чинника на науковий та культурний розвиток суспільства, становлення демократичних засад громадського суспільства.

Висновки. Виявлено витоки становлення бібліотечної цензури в Україні. Досліджено основні етапи, форми і напрями втілення духовної та світської цензури. Проаналізовано вплив цензури Російської імперії на формування мережі публічних бібліотек і вилучення україномовної літератури з фондів публічних бібліотек. Прослідковано принципи роботи централізованої системи цензурних органів, які регламентували напрями діяльності публічних бібліотек, зокрема акцентовано увагу на створенні міністерських каталогів згідно з якими відбувалась чистка книжкових фондів. Розкрито сутність бібліотечної цензурної політики російського уряду яка була спрямована на знищення публічних бібліотек України як важливих осередків української духовності. З'ясовано принципи роботи радянських цензурних інституцій, що регламентували напрями роботи українських бібліотек, перетворюючи їх на заклади політосвіти.

Ключові слова: цензура; царська цензура; радянські цензурні інституції; публічні бібліотеки; бібліотечна справа; «чистка» фонду; міністерські каталоги.

ИСТОКИ И СТАНОВЛЕНИЕ БИБЛИОТЕЧНОЙ ЦЕНЗУРЫ В УКРАИНЕ

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Цель статьи. Исследовать историю становления цензуры при формировании информационно-библиотечной политики. Методологической основой является совокупность произведенных современной наукой принципов и методов научного исследования. Принцип историзма выражен в учете всех конкретно-исторических факторов для определения этапов становления библиотечной цензуры на Украине, выделения в них общих черт и отличий. Метод объективности нашел отражение во взвешенной оценке и беспристрастном анализе форм и направлений воплощения духовной и светской цензуры. Также использован аналитический метод для определения принципов работы централизованной системы цензурных органов, которые регламентировали направления деятельности публичных библиотек, в частности создание министерских каталогов, согласно которым происходила чистка книжных фондов. Научная новизна заключается в выявлении влияния библиотечной цензуры как тормозящего фактора в научном и культурном развитии, формировании демократических основ гражданского общества.

Выводы. Выявлены истоки становления библиотечной цензуры в Украине. Исследованы основные этапы, формы и направления воплощения духовной и светской цензуры. Проанализировано влияние цензуры Российской империи на формирование сети публичных библиотек и изъятия украиноязычной литературы из фондов публичных библиотек. Прослежены принципы работы централизованной системы цензурных органов, которые регламентировали направления деятельности публичных библиотек, в частности акцентировано внимание на создании министерских каталогов, согласно которым происходила чистка книжных фондов. Раскрыта сущность библиотечной цензурной политики российского правительства, которая была направлена на уничтожение публичных библиотек Украины как важных центров украинской духовности. Выяснены принципы работы советских цензурных учреждений, регламентирующих направления работы украинских библиотек, превращающих их в учреждения политпросвещения.

Ключевые слова: цензура; царская цензура; советские цензурные учреждения; публичные библиотеки; библиотечное дело; «чистка» фонда; министерские каталоги.